

Research Article

Soil Chemical Properties and Garden Egg (*Solanum* spp) Performance under Different Organic Amendments

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Abstract

Field experiments were conducted during the growing seasons of 2012 and 2013 at the experimental farm of National Horticultural Research Institute Mbato out-Station Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria to evaluate the effect of different organic amendments on some soil chemical properties and performance of five garden egg varieties. The treatments were five garden egg varieties (*Solanum gilo*, *Solanum aethiopicum*, *Solanum macrocarpon*, *Solanum Ex-Lantan* and *Solanum melongena*) and three organic amendments (cattle dung, poultry manure, pig waste) with a control (no manure). The experiment was a split-plot fitted in randomized complete block design replicated four times. Data were collected at 4, 6 and 8 weeks after transplanting (WAT) on plant height (cm), plant girth (cm), number of leaves, number of branches and leaf area, data on fruit weight/plot, numbers of fruits, fruit diameter (cm), fruit length (cm), length of peduncle as well as dry matter yield were also collected while soil samples collected from each plot before and after the experiments were analyzed. The results revealed that the effect of different soil amendments and garden egg varieties showed significant ($p < 0.05$) interaction on some soil chemical properties, growth and yield performance of garden egg. Poultry manure application increased Nitrogen (N) and soil pH in plots with *S. gilo*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. macrocarpon* while in plots that received cattle dung, N and organic carbon (OC) was high in plots with *S. aethiopicum* and *S. melongena*. In plots treated with poultry manure, number of leaves, number of branches and plant height at 4, 6 and 8 WAT was highest in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, *S. macrocarpon* and *S. Ex-lantan* Plots. Cattle dung application increased fruit girth in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon* plots while fruit weight and fruit length was favoured by pig waste in *S. gilo* and *S. aethiopicum*

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

plots. *Solanum gilo* showed better performance in terms of number of leaves, number of fruits, fruit weight as well as quick maturity. It is therefore recommended for production in Okigwe zone, South Eastern Nigeria.

Key words: Garden egg varieties, Amendments, Growth and yield performance, Soil chemical properties.

Received: 23/04/18

Accepted: 02/08/18

Introduction

Garden egg (*Solanum Spp.*) a native of India is a popular vegetable crop grown in West Africa and the world over. It is one of the five most important indigenous vegetable crops which belong to the family Solanaceae and can be grown together with tomatoes, onions, pepper and okra (Messiaen, 2012). It can tolerate both drought and excessive rainfall.

In Nigeria, different local varieties are in existence and are grown by different ethnic groups for local consumption and other uses. The fruits can be eaten raw as a vegetable. It could also be boiled, fried and stuffed before consumption (Rice *et al.*, 2007). The leaves of some varieties could also be eaten raw or boiled, hence they are known to provide all the nutritionally important amino-acids, vitamins and minerals in adequate quantities (Udom and Bello, 2009). In addition, the alkaloid solanin extracted from the roots, and fruits are used for therapeutic purposes (Yayock *et al.*, 2008). Garden egg supplements starchy foods and also is a cheap source of protein, vitamins and minerals. The prominence of the crop as a vegetable is essentially due to its prolific fruit production, large size of the fruit and quick maturing. In the South-eastern Nigeria, the crop is highly cherished and commonly served during traditional/religious ceremonies, title taking/chieftaincy ceremonies, child dedication, wedding ceremonies, burial ceremonies, thanksgiving ceremonies, birthday ceremonies and during meetings. However, garden egg consumption in Nigeria is on the increase and the quest for its increased production is often constrained by low nutrient status of our soils. The recognition of the high nutritive value of this crop made it one of the crops in demand in the market year round.

Nutrient elements have been established to be important in garden egg cultivation (Omotayo and Chukwuka, 2009). While Nitrogen is important in vegetative development, phosphorus is needed to stimulate flowering and fruit formation and potassium is for seed setting. The ultisols which dominate agricultural lands of south eastern Nigeria cover more than 70% of the total land area (Mbagwu, 1992), but they

suffer the constraint of low reserves of essential plant nutrients and high soil acidity. Use of organic manure is recommended for managing such soils to improve the nutrients content and sustain yield, especially with current high costs of inorganic fertilizers (Omotayo and Chukwuka, 2009). The high cost and scarcity of inorganic fertilizers in developing countries prohibit their use by most peasant farmers, thereby generating renewed interest in the use of organic materials as nutrient sources for the cultivation of nutrient demanding crops like garden egg (Saidu *et al.*, 2010). Organic fertilizers supply organic matter to the soil that modifies soils physical and chemical properties (Onwuka *et al.*, 2008). The use of organic manures enhance soil productivity, increase the soil organic carbon content, enhances the activities of soil micro-organisms, improves the soil crumb structure and nutrient status of soil as well as crop yield (Akani and Ojeniyi, 2007). Addition of Organic manures to the soil lower soil bulk density, increased aggregate stability and macro pores (Olayinka *et al.*, 2006). The objectives of this research are to; (1) Determine the effects of different organic amendments on the growth, the yield of garden egg. (2) Determine the effects of this amendment on soil properties after cropping (post soil cropping properties).

Materials and Methods

Location and site description

The experiment was conducted in the 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons at the experimental field of National Horticultural Research Institute, Mbato Sub-Station Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. The station lies on latitude 05° 33' N and Longitude 07° 23' E and altitude of 130 meters above sea level. The area enjoys over 2, 200 mm of mean annual rainfall with temperature range of between 21°C and 32°C. The experimental site had been under fallow for 3 years overgrown with Elephant grass (*Panicum maximum*). The site was well drained, non-gravelly soil. The soil texture was sandy loam (743 g/kg sand, 155g/kg silt. 122 g/kg clay) characterized by low organic matter, low cation exchange capacity (CEC) and are highly leached with soil pH of 4.38.

Field Experiment

The field was prepared by slashing using a tractor. It was then ploughed and harrowed. Soil samples were collected using soil sampling auger to a depth of 0-30cm before planting in both 2012 and 2013.

Experimental design, field establishment and agronomic measurements The experiments comprised of treatments involving five garden egg varieties (*Solanum gilo*, *Solanum aethiopicum*, *Solanum macrocarpon*, *Solanum Ex-Lantan* and *Solanum*

melongena) and three organic amendments (cattle dung, poultry manure and pig waste). Arranged in split -plot fitted in randomized complete block design replicated four times, with the garden egg varieties in the main plot and the soil amendments in the sub plot. Each plot size measured 4 m x 4 m. Garden egg seedlings from the nursery were transplanted in a spacing of 1 m x 1 m two weeks after manure application to the plots. The various amendments were applied at 20 t/ha rate. The experimental plots were weeded at 4, 8 and 12 WAT. Data were collected at 4, 6 and 8 WAT on plant height, plant girth, number of leaves, leaf area and number of branches. Also, fruit weight/plot, number of fruits, number of calyx, fruit diameter, fruit length and length of peduncle were measured. Soil samples were collected and analyzed as mentioned earlier.

Soil Sample Analysis

The soil samples collected from the field were air dried; sieved using a 2mm mesh sized sieve and then subjected to routine laboratory analysis. The particle size distribution was determined by hydrometer method according to the procedure of Gee and Or, (2002). Sodium hexametaphosphate was used as dispersant. The soil pH was determined in 1:2 soil water ratio suspension using glass electrode pH meter (Mclean 1965). Organic carbon was determined using chromic wet oxidation method (Nelson and Somers, 1982). Total soil Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl digestion method (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982). Available phosphorus was determined on Bray -1 extractant method. Exchangeable K^+ , and Na^+ were extracted using 1N ammonium acetate (NH_4OAc) and then determined using flame photometer (Thomas, 1982). Exchangeable Mg^{+} and Ca^{+} were determined using ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA). Exchangeable acidity was measured titrimetrically using 1 normal potassium chloride (1N KCl) against 0.05N sodium hydroxide (Mclean, 1965). Soil temperature was determined using soil thermometer in -situ at 0.10 m depth, while bulk density at 0 - 15 cm was determined using core sampler, and samples were oven dried for 48 hours at 105 °C.

Organic Manure Analysis

The nutrients were extracted by dry ashing method. Air dried ground manure samples were sieved through a 2mm sieve and ignited at 450°C for 2 hours. The ash was extracted with hydrochloric acid (HCl). Organic matter (OM) was determined by Walkley - Black dichromate digestion method and total nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method. The phosphorus (P) was determined by ammonium Molybdate/ ammonium vanadate blue method. Potassium was determined using the flame photometer and calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) by EDTA titration. The pH in 0.01M $CaCl_2$ was determined using a glass electrode pH meter.

Statistical Analysis

All data collected on various parameters were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Genstat Package Software Programme (2010). The means were separated using least significant difference (LSD) at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Soil properties used for the study

Some properties of the soil used for the trial is shown in Table 1. The soil is acidic in reaction with pH values in 1:1 soil-water ratio of 4.38. The soil organic carbon (SOC) content was low, with values of 1.60 g/kg. The total nitrogen content was generally low, with values of 0.90 g/kg. The total nitrogen content followed the same trend as SOC content. The available phosphorus content (mg/kg) of the soil was low, with values of 6.80. Exchangeable cations (calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium) contents were low, with calcium and magnesium dominating the exchange complex. Calcium content was 3.20 cmol/kg. Magnesium content was 1.60 cmol/kg, potassium was 0.19 cmol/kg, while sodium content was 0.06 cmol/kg. Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) value was also low, with value of 5.75 cmol/kg. The texture of the soil showed that the soil is sandy loam. Bulk density value was 1.59 mg/m³.

The low SOC content could be attributed to the inherent characteristics of the soil and climatic conditions which result to the high rate of organic matter decomposition associated with the tropical agricultural production systems. Arable soils of Southeastern Nigeria are mostly sandy, acidic ultisols with low organic matter and nutrient status (Nottidge *et al.*, (2005; 2007). These soil conditions are also dominant in the rainforest zones of the humid tropics (Nottidge *et al.*, (2005). The low nitrogen content could be attributed to a number of factors such as the high rate of SOM decomposition as a result of rainfall and temperature conditions as well as high leaching and microbial activities prevalent in the tropics. The low values of exchangeable cations and ECEC are closely associated to the low soil OM contents as well as highly weathered and leached nature of the soil. The narrow C: N ratio is indicative of the high rate of mineralization of organic matter.

Table 1: Some properties of the soil used for the experiment

Soil Properties	Values
pH(H ₂ O)	4.38
Organic carbon (gkg ⁻¹)	1.60
Total N (gkg ⁻¹)	0.90
Available P(mgkg ⁻¹)	6.80
Ca (cmolkg ⁻¹)	3.20
Mg (cmolkg ⁻¹)	1.60
K (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.19
Na (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.06
ECEC (cmolkg ⁻¹)	5.75
Base saturation (%)	58.2
C/N ratio	
Sand (g/kg)	
Silt (g/kg)	155
Clay (g/kg)	102
Exchangeable Mn (cmol/kg)	1.08
Exchangeable Zn (cmol/kg)	1.70
Exchangeable Fe (cmol/kg)	6.23
Exchangeable Cu (cmol/kg)	18.75
Bulk density	1.59

Chemical properties of the organic material used for the study

As shown in Table 2, nitrogen content was highest (1.5%) in poultry manure and lowest (1.0 %) in pig waste. Calcium content was highest (30.5 cmol/kg) in poultry manure and lowest (16.0 cmol/kg) in cattle dung. Magnesium was highest (9.4 cmol/kg) in cattle dung and lowest (6.0 cmol/kg) in piggery waste. Potassium was highest (29.2 cmol/kg) in poultry manure and lowest (23.0 cmol/kg) in cattle dung, while sodium was highest (4.9 cmol/kg) in cattle dung and lowest (4.2 cmol/kg) in poultry manure. Among the three organic amendments, poultry manure seems to be the best in terms of nutrient content when compared with others.

Table 2: Some properties of the organic amendments used for the experiment

Properties	Poultry manure	Cattle dung	Pig waste
pH (H ₂ O)	8.1	9.8	6.1
Organic carbon (%)	14.9	7.8	7.3
Total N (%)	1.5	1.2	1.0
Available P(mgkg ⁻¹)	34.6	15.8	6.0
Ca(cmolk ⁻¹)	30.5	16.0	28.0
Mg(cmolk ⁻¹)	7.6	9.4	6.0
K(cmolk ⁻¹)	29.2	23.0	25.0
Na(cmolk ⁻¹)	4.2	4.9	4.4
C/N ratio	4:1	5:4	3:4
Exchangeable Mn (cmol/kg)	66.3	76	59
Exchangeable Zn (cmol/kg)	5.4	5.9	3.9
Exchangeable Fe (cmol/kg)	7.6	3.2	6.0
Exchangeable Cu (cmol/kg)	1.7	0.8	1.3

Soil chemical properties after the experiment

The effect of different soil amendments and garden egg varieties on soil nitrogen, soil organic carbon and exchangeable acidity is presented in Table 3. A significant interaction of manure and garden egg varieties on total N shows that soil N content on plots with amendments depends on the garden egg variety grown on the plot. In plots that received poultry manure, N was high in plots planted with *S. gilo* and *S. melongena*. Similarly, in plots that received cattle dung, N was high in plots planted with *S. aethiopicum* and *S. melongena*. Generally, highest mean nitrogen value of 0.71 g/kg was recorded with poultry manure while the least (0.43 g/kg) was recorded with the control. Plots with *S. melongena* showed the highest mean nitrogen value of 0.69 g/kg and the least value (0.47 g/kg) was recorded with *S.Ex-Lantan* Plots. The improved N value in the amended plots could be attributed to the high N content in the organic manure applied. (Fening *et al.*, 2011) reported significant increase in soil available nitrogen due to organic manure application.

Also, soil organic carbon showed significant interaction on the soil amendments and garden egg varieties (Table 3). The amendments improved the SOC relative to the control. Moreso, there were significant differences between poultry manure and pig waste on SOC in plots with *S. gilo*. Significant differences also existed between pig waste and the control in *S.aethiopicum* plots. The plots amended with pig waste showed increase in organic carbon in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon* plots while poultry manure application increased OC in plots planted with *S.Ex-Lantan*.

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Similarly, cattle dung application increased OC in plots with *S. melongena*. The increase in value of soil organic carbon can be attributed to the high OC content of animal manure sources added to the soil. (Danjuma *et al.*, 2012) reported that the addition of organic manures resulted in significant increase in SOC. (Dauda *et al.*, 2008) reported that poultry manure enhances soil productivity, increases the SOC content, OM and nutrient status of the soil as well as crop yield. The different animal manure sources and garden egg varieties also showed significant interaction on exchange acidity of the soil (Table 3). The garden egg varieties responded differently to the sources of animal manures. Pig waste application increased exchangeable acidity in the *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. melongena* plots while cattle dung favoured exch. acidity in plots planted with *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. macrocarpon*. Application of the different animal manures increased the exchangeable acidity of the soil relative to control with highest mean value recorded in pig waste. However, *S. gilo* plot showed highest mean exchangeable acidity value of 1.43 cmol/kg. The increase in exchangeable acidity is in line with earlier findings of (Adesodun *et al.*, 2005) who reported that application of organic manures to the soil increased soil OM content, exchangeable acidity and N, P, K values. Organic manures improved soil physical and chemical properties with yearly application giving cumulative positive effect (Agbede *et al.*, 2008)

TABLE 3: Effect Of Different Organic Amendments and Garden Egg Varieties on Mean Nitrogen (N) (g/kg), ORGANIC Carbon (OC) (g/kg) and Exchangeable Acidity(EA) (cmol/kg) IN 2012 AND 2013.

Varieties	Organic Amendments												Control			
	Cattle dung				Poultry manure				Pig waste				N	OC	EA	Mean
	N	OC	EA	Mean	N	OC	EA	Mean	N	OC	EA	Mean	N	OC	EA	Mean
<i>S.gilo</i>	0.54	10.60	1.46	4.2	0.8	9.92	1.52	4.1	0.5	12.9	1.62	5.1	0.47	11.2	1.10	4.3
<i>S.aethiopicum</i>	0.70	11.03	1.42	4.3	0.6	12.9	1.40	4.9	0.5	13.7	1.42	5.22	0.47	9.71	1.14	3.8
<i>S.Ex-Lantan</i>	0.45	10.30	1.52	4.09	0.5	10.8	1.46	4.3	0.5	10.7	1.46	4.24	0.39	10.1	1.11	3.9
<i>S.macrocarpon</i>	0.51	11.85	1.34	4.56	0.7	11.9	1.20	4.6	0.6	14.2	1.20	5.34	0.40	9.20	1.10	3.6
<i>S.melongena</i>	1.10	10.70	1.18	4.33	0.8	9.27	1.18	3.7	0.4	8.12	1.62	3.39	0.39	9.6	1.28	3.76
Mean	0.65	10.89	1.38		0.7	10.9	1.35		0.5	11.9	1.46		0.43	9.94	1.15	
					1	8			3	6						
					N	OC	EA									
VARIETY					0.209	1.863	0.19									
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES					0.218	2.183	0.13									
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES X VARIETY					0.419	3.846	0.36									

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The effect of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on potassium content of the soil is shown in Table 4. There were significant interaction between the different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on K content. Poultry manure application increased K in plots with *S. aethiopicum*, *S. macrocarpon* and *S. melongena* while pig waste amendment increased K in plots with *S. gilo* and *S. Ex-Lantan*. Generally, the organic amendments increased K content relative to the control. This could be attributed to the high K content of the amendments. This finding is in line with the report of (Adesodun *et al.*, 2005) who reported that application of organic manures to the soil increased soil OM content, N, P, K and Ca. From the results obtained, poultry manure application also significantly increased soil pH in plots with *S. gilo*, *S.aethiopicum*, *S.Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena*. Cattle dung application increased soil pH in *S.macrocarpon* plots (Table 4). The increase in soil pH values in plots treated with organic amendments could be attributed to the ability of the manures to improve soil properties (Akande and Adedrian, 2004) found that poultry manure significantly increased soil pH, N, P, K, Ca and Mg content. Poultry manure gave the highest mean available phosphorus value of 21.3 mg/kg followed by cattle dung (20.58). *Solanum Ex-Lantan* recorded highest mean P value of 21.21 mg/kg (Table 4). There were significant interaction between the organic amendments and garden egg varieties on available P .Poultry manure application increased available P in plots with *S.gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, *S.Ex-Lantan* and *S. macrocarpon* while pig waste application increased available P in *S.melongena* plot. However, all the organic amendments increased available P relative to the control. The increase in the P content of the soil can be as a result of high P content in the amendments applied which in turn improved the soil P (Akande and Adedrian 2004) found that poultry manure significantly increased soil pH, N, P, K, Ca and Mg content. (Gupta and Shukla, 2007) observed that poultry manure is very rich animal manure by giving considerable increase in soil organic matter, available P and exchangeable cations.

TABLE 4: Effect of Different Organic Amendments and Garden Egg Varieties on Mean Potassium (K) (cmol/kg), Soil pH , and Available Phosphorus(P) (m/kg) in 2012 AND 2013.

ORGANIC AMENDMENTS																
VARIETIES	Cattle dung				Poultry manure				Pig waste				Control			
	K	pH	P	MEA	K	pH	P	ME	K	pH	P	MEA	K	pH	P	MEAN
				N				AN				N				
<i>S.gilo</i>	0.12	4.67	20.7	8.49	0.13	4.82	22.3	9.08	0.26	4.72	16.3	7.09	0.11	4.35	15.5	6.65
<i>S.aethiopicum</i>	0.14	4.65	20.1	8.30	0.19	4.82	22.4	9.14	0.09	4.70	18.2	7.66	0.10	4.5	18.4	7.67
<i>S.Ex-Lantan</i>	0.12	4.70	24.2	9.67	0.14	4.90	25.3	10.11	0.16	4.67	18.9	7.91	0.11	4.15	16.5	6.92
<i>S.macrocarpon</i>	0.11	5.00	19.2	8.10	0.17	4.67	19.2	8.0	0.13	4.85	17.6	7.53	0.10	4.40	16.6	7.03
<i>S.melongena</i>	0.14	4.65	18.7	7.83	0.17	4.85	17.2	7.41	0.10	4.65	20.0	8.25	0.01	4.40	17.4	7.27
Mean	0.13	4.73	20.5		0.16	4.82	21.3		0.14	4.72	18.2		0.08	4.27	16.8	
					K	pH		P								
LSD(0.05) VARIETY					0.07	0.14		2.64								
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES					0.07	0.26		2.49								
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES X VARIETY					0.14	0.34		5.20								

Growth parameters

The effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on number of leaves of garden egg at 4, 6 and 8 WAT in 2012 and 2013 is shown on Table 5. Poultry manure and pig waste showed significant differences on number of leaves in *S. aethiopicum* plots. Poultry manure increased number of leaves in plots planted to *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon*. Moreso, cattle dung application increased number of leaves in plots with *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena*. Generally, the organic amendments increased the number of leaves of garden egg relative to the control. The highest number of leaves recorded with poultry manure and *Solanum aethiopicum* interaction could be attributed to the plants' morphology which gives it an advantage of having many branches and leaves.

The increase in the number of leaves of garden egg in plots treated with poultry manure indicates that organic manure was able to release enough nutrients for the growth of the garden egg. (John *et al.*, 2004), reported that poultry manure contains essential nutrients elements associated with high photosynthetic activities and thus promotes root and vegetative growth. At six 6 WAT, the different manure sources and garden egg varieties showed significant interaction on number of leaves. *Solanum aethiopicum* showed significant differences compared with *Solanum gilo* on number of leaves in the plots treated with cattle dung. There were significant differences between cattle dung and poultry manure application in *S. melongena* plots. The combination of poultry manure and *Solanum aethiopicum* at 6 WAT recorded the highest number of leaves (94.9) compared with other manure sources. The application of the different manure sources increased the number of leaves at 6 WAT relative to the control. Poultry manure application favoured the increase in number of leaves of garden egg across all the varieties. (John *et al.*, 2004), reported that poultry manure contains essential nutrient elements associated with high photosynthetic activities and thus promotes root and vegetative growth. From the results obtained at 8 WAT, poultry manure application increased number of leaves in plots that received *S.gilo*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena*, with highest mean value of 138.1. Pig waste however, recorded increase in number of leaves in plots planted with *S. aethiopicum* and *S.macrocarpon*. *S aethiopicum* showed highest mean number of leaves value of 164.8. The application of the different organic manure sources increased the number of leaves of garden egg varieties at 8 WAT. (Aliyu, 2010) reported that poultry manure has profound effect on the vegetative development of garden egg and it ensures healthy and vigorous growth of the crop.

TABLE 5: Effect of Different Organic Amendments and Garden Egg Varieties on Mean Number of Leaves of Garden Egg At 4,6 and 8 Weeks After transplanting (WAT) in 2012 AND 2013.

ORGANIC AMENDMENTS																
VARIETIES	CATTLE DUNG				POULTRY MANURE				PIG WASTE				CONTROL			
	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean
<i>S.gilo</i>	4.29	55.7	155.2	71.7	4.55	68.6	170	81.0	4.38	44.3	105.1	51.3	4.0	46.7	103.2	51.3
<i>S.aethiopicum</i>	4.73	82.4	161.4	82.8	7.10	94.9	175	92.5	5.69	71.7	179	85.5	5.16	69.5	143	72.5
<i>S.EX-Lantan</i>	3.81	47.5	67.7	39.7	3.52	52.9	90.3	48.9	3.56	37.3	57.8	32.9	3.41	31.3	51.4	28.7
<i>S.macrocarpon</i>	4.29	44.3	82.2	43.6	4.95	60.9	128.	64.8	3.49	48.7	58.0	36.8	2.80	38.2	72.4	37.8
<i>S.melongena</i>	3.89	45.1	82.2	43.7	3.78	63.0	126.	64.3	2.71	39.8	68.7	37.1	2.30	37.7	63.9	34.6
Mean	4.19	55.0	109.5		4.78	68.1	138.		3.96	48.3	98.1		3.53	44.7	88.7	
							4									
							2									
							1									
							4 WAT									
							6 WAT									
							8 WAT									
							LSD(0.05) VARIETY									
							0.63									
							LSD(0.05) MANURE									
							0.81									
							SOURCES									
							LSD(0.05) MANURE									
							1.4									
							SOURCES X VARIETY									

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On the number of branches of garden egg at 4, 6 and 8WAT in 2012 and 2013, application of different amendments and garden egg increased the number of branches relative to the control (Table 6). There were significant interaction between the manure sources and garden egg varieties on number of branches at 4 WAT. There were also marked differences between poultry manure and cattle dung on number of branches in plot planted with *S. aethiopicum*. Plots that received cattle dung planted with *S.Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena* increased number of branches while, poultry manure application increased number of branches in *S. gilo*, *S.aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon* plots. Poultry manure was able to release enough nutrients for the growth of the garden egg. It has earlier been reported by (Aliyu, 2010) that poultry manure has profound effect on the vegetative development of garden egg and it ensures healthy and vigorous growth of the crop. The different organic amendments increased the number of branches at 6 WAT relative to control. Poultry manure amendment increased number of branches of garden egg in plots that received *S. aethiopicum*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena* while cattle dung application increased number of branches in plots with *S. gilo*. Poultry manure promotes vigorous growth, increase meristematic and physiological activities in the plant due to supply of plant nutrient and improvement in soil properties (Dauda *et al.*, 2008). At 8 WAT, poultry manure showed significant increases in the number of branches across all the varieties, with highest mean value of 24.3. The increase in number of branches favoured by poultry manure application could be attributed to the ability of the organic manure to improve the soil properties and promote vigorous growth and physiological activities in the plant. (John *et al.*, 2004), reported that poultry manure has positive effects on growth and yield of garden egg which could be due to the fact that poultry manure contains essential nutrient elements that favour high photosynthetic activities that promotes prolific root and vegetative growth.

TABLE 6: Effect of Different Organic Amendments and Garden Egg Varieties on Mean Number of Branches of Garden Egg at 4, 6 and 8 Weeks After transplanting (WAT) in 2012 AND 2013.

ORGANIC AMENDMENTS																
VARIETIES	CATTLE DUNG				POULTRY MANURE				PIG WASTE				CONTROL			
	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean
<i>S.gilo</i>	4.29	15.9	27.5	15.9	4.55	15.7	27.9	16.1	4.38	11.7	22.6	12.9	4.0	10.6	21.9	12.2
<i>S.aethiopicum</i>	4.73	19.5	26.1	16.8	7.10	22.5	32.7	20.8	5.16	18.1	31.2	18.2	5.09	17.1	20.7	14.3
<i>S.EX-Lantan</i>	3.81	7.7	9.7	7.07	3.52	10.0	14.8	9.44	3.56	7.3	8.4	6.4	3.42	6.6	7.8	5.9
<i>S.macrocarpon</i>	4.29	12.0	17.7	11.3	4.95	16.8	24.5	15.4	3.49	12.3	15.6	10.5	2.80	10.6	14.9	9.4
<i>S.melongena</i>	3.89	12.4	12.4	10.2	3.78	14.9	21.5	13.4	3.78	9.0	11.3	8.0	2.30	8.3	10.7	7.1
Mean	4.19	13.5	19.1		4.78	16.0	24.3		3.86	11.7	17.8		3.16	10.7	15.2	
					4 WAT	6 WAT	8 WAT									
LSD(0.05) VARIETY				0.81	2.4	4.25										
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES				0.63	1.9	3.62										
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES X VARIETY				1.36	4.1	7.62										

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The effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean plant girth at 4, 6 and 8 WAT in 2012 and 2013 are shown in figure 1. Cattle dung application showed highest increase in plant girth in the plot planted with *S.melongena*. Poultry manure application favoured plant girth at 4 WAT in *S. gilo* plot while piggery waste application showed increase in plant girth in plots planted with *S. macrocarpon*. The different garden egg varieties responded differently to organic amendments. Relative to the control, the different amendments increased the plant girth of garden egg. At 6 weeks after transplanting, poultry manure application significantly increased plant girth in plots planted up with *S. gilo*. Poultry manure also favoured plant girth in *S. aethiopicum* and *S.melongena* plots while cattle dung application increased plant girth in plots planted to *S.gilo*.

The plant height of garden egg as affected by different organic amendments and garden egg varieties at 4, 6 and 8 weeks after transplanting is shown in Table 7.

Fig. 1: Effect of manure sources on the girth of egg plant varieties at 4, 6, and 8 weeks after planting

Poultry manure application increased the plant height in *S.gilo*, *S.aethiopicum*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena* plots while cattle dung application increased plant height in *S. macrocarpon* plot. There were significant interaction between the amendments and garden egg varieties. The application of different manure sources increased the plant height relative to the control. The better performance of garden egg plant height with poultry manure application can be attributed to the higher nutrient composition in poultry manure and its ability to provide enough nutrients for the plant growth. (Dauda *et al.*, 2008) reported that poultry manure promotes vigorous growth, increase meristematic and physiological activities in the plant due to supply of plant nutrient and improvement in soil properties. Moreso, (John *et al.*, 2004), reported that poultry manure contains essential nutrient elements associated with high photosynthetic activities and vegetative growth. At 6 WAT, poultry manure

application favoured plant height in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, *S. macrocarpon* and *S. melongena* plots. Cattle dung amendment increased plant height in *S. Ex-Lantan* plots. Cattle dung and poultry manure application showed no significant differences in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. Ex-Lantan* plots but showed significant differences in plots planted with *S. macrocarpon* and *S. melongena*. The organic amendments and garden egg varieties showed significant interactions. The better growth performance of plots treated with organic amendments is a confirmation that organic manure modifies soils physical and chemical properties], enhances soil productivity, and nutrient status of the soil as well as crop yield (Dauda *et al.*, 2008). Moreso, at 8 WAT, poultry manure increased the plant height across the varieties. The interaction of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on plant height was significant. The increase in plant height could be attributed to the ability of the organic amendments to improve the soil properties and promote vigorous growth and physiological activities in the plant. (John *et al.*, 2004) reported that poultry manure has positive effects on growth and yield of garden egg which could be due to the fact that poultry manure contains essential nutrient elements that favour high photosynthetic activities that promotes prolific root and vegetative growth.

TABLE 7: Effect of Different Organic Amendments and Garden Egg Varieties on Mean Plant Height (CM) Of Garden Egg At 4,6 And 8 Weeks After transplanting (WAT) in 2012 AND 2013.

ORGANIC AMENDMENTS																
VARIETIES	CATTLE DUNG				POULTRY MANURE				PIG WASTE				CONTROL			
	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean	4	6	8	Mean
<i>S.gilo</i>	29.7	67.5	122	73.1	38.5	67.7	126	77.3	30.6	54.8	113.3	66.2	26.6	53.6	108.6	62.7
<i>S.aethiopicum</i>	32	64.5	96.4	64.3	36.1	64.6	102	67.5	33.7	54.3	86.9	58.3	28.3	51.5	83.8	54.5
<i>S.EX-Lantan</i>	23.3	39.1	54.7	117.3	28.2	36.7	64.4	43.1	27.6	38.9	53.3	39.9	21.5	27.4	52.1	33.7
<i>S.macrocarpon</i>	27.7	43.6	89	53.4	26.6	53.9	95.9	58.8	27.5	49.8	82.7	53.3	21.1	42.5	82.7	48.7
<i>S.melongena</i>	21.4	38.6	63.9	41.3	25.9	50.2	105.	60.7	22.4	37.2	64.5	41.6	19.6	37.8	64.5	40.6
Mean	26.9	50.6	85.2		31.0	54.6	98.7		28.4	47.0	78.3		23.8	42.5	78.3	
							6									
							4 WAT									
							6 WAT									
							8 WAT									
LSD(0.05) VARIETY				3.1			5.9					10.1				
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES				3.2			4.1					10.1				
LSD(0.05) MANURE SOURCES X VARIETY				6.2			11.3					20.4				

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The effect of application of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on leaf area at 4; 6 and 8 WAT in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Fig. 2. Poultry manure application significantly increased the leaf area of garden egg in *S. gilo* plot. Pig wastes however favoured leaf area in *S. macrocarpon* plot while cattle dung increased leaf area in *S. gilo* plot. The garden egg varieties responded differently to sources of organic manure. At 6 WAT, the result indicates that plots planted with *S. aethiopicum* showed the least increase in leaf area across the manure sources. Poultry manure application gave the highest leaf area in *S. gilo* plot. *Solanum melongena* showed similar performance in cattle dung and poultry manure treated plots. Application of organic manure increased leaf area of garden egg relative to the control. At 8 WAT the leaf area of *Solanum gilo* significantly increased with the application of organic manure sources. However, pig wastes and poultry manure increased leaf area in plots planted to *S. melongena* while *S. aethiopicum* showed least values in all the manure sources. The result shows that there were significant interaction between the organic manure sources and garden egg varieties. This result confirms that organic manures improve soil physical and chemical properties and contains essential nutrient elements that favour high photosynthetic activities that promotes root and vegetative growth (John et al., 2004; Dauda et al., 2008). The increase in leaf area in plots with organic amendment indicates that organic manure promotes vigorous growth, increase meristematic and physiological activities in the plant due to supply of plant nutrient and improvement in soil properties (Dauda et al., 2008).

Fig. 2: Effect of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean leaf area of garden egg at 4, 6 and 8WAT

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Yield parameters

The effect of application of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean dry matter yield of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Table 8. Poultry manure significantly increased the dry matter yield of garden egg in all the varieties. There were significant differences in dry matter yield between poultry manure and cattle dung across all the varieties. The manure sources and garden egg varieties showed significant interaction on the dry matter yield. Poultry manure interaction with *Solanum gilo* gave the highest dry matter yield of 8.83 t/ha. The manure application increased the dry matter yield of garden compared to the control. The increase in the dry matter yield goes further to confirm that organic manure increased nutrient concentration in the soil, improve nutrient uptake by plants and increased crop yields (Udom and Bello, 2009; Nyakatawa et al., 2010 ; Ayoola, and Adeniyani 2006)..

Table 8: Effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean dry matter yield (t/ha) in 2012 and 2013

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex - Lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpo n</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	4.9	4.1	3.6	3.2	6.2	4.4
Poultry manure	8.8	5.4	5.5	6.4	7.5	6.7
Pig waste	4.6	4.0	4.3	3.5	4.2	9.1
Control	4.0	3.2	3.0	3.1	3.6	3.4
Mean	5.6	4.1	4.1	4.0	5.4	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 0.77

LSD (0.05) Variety = 0.70

LSD (0.05) Manure amendment x variety = 1.45

The effect of application of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on fruit girth of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Table 9. Cattle dung increased fruit girth in plots planted with *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon*. Poultry manure increased fruit girth in plots planted to *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena*. Poultry manure and piggery wastes application showed no significant differences in *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. Ex-Lantan* plots. There were significant interaction between the different organic manure sources and garden egg varieties. From the results obtained, application of the manure sources increased the fruit girth of garden egg

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relative to the control. The higher fruit girth observed with *Solanum melongena* may be related to fruit size which is one outstanding feature of the plant (Lewis, 2005). Organic manure application was able to release enough nutrients for the growth of the garden egg. Aliyu (2010) reported that poultry manure has profound effect on the vegetative development of garden egg and it ensures healthy and vigorous growth of the crop.

Table 9: Effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean fruit girth (cm) of garden egg

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex - Lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpo n</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	3.9	2.1	4.4	3.0	6.1	3.9
Poultry manure	3.7	2.0	4.6	2.9	6.2	3.9
Pig waste	3.6	1.9	4.6	2.9	6.2	3.8
Control	3.3	1.8	4.4	2.8	5.6	3.6
Mean	3.6	2.0	4.5	2.9	6.1	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 0.25

LSD (0.05) Variety = 0.28

LSD (0.05) Manure sources x variety = 0.56

Effect of organic amendments application and garden egg varieties on fruit length of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Table 10. Cattle dung application favoured fruit length in *S. macrocarpon* plot. Poultry manure increased fruit length in *S. aethiopicum*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. melongena* plots while piggery wastes favoured fruit length in *S. gilo* plot. There were no significant differences in fruit length between cattle dung and poultry manure in plots planted to *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. Ex-Lantan*. The interaction effect of cattle dung and garden egg varieties were significant. Application of organic amendments increased the fruit length of the garden egg varieties relative to the control. The interaction effect of poultry manure and *Solanum melongena* showed the highest fruit length of 15.9 cm. The better performance of *Solanum melongena* in terms of fruit length can be attributes to its natural feature of elongated, bell shaped fruit (Lewis, 2005, Bukenya, and Bonsu ,2004) . The organic amendments increased soil productivity and crop yield. The soil

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fertility improving value of cattle dung and poultry manure have been confirmed by (Akanbi, 2002).

Table 10: Effect of different organic manure amendments and garden egg varieties on mean fruit length (cm) of garden egg in 2012 and 2013

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex-Lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpon</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	5.9	3.3	6.3	6.2	14.6	7.2
Poultry manure	6.0	3.4	6.3	6.1	15.9	7.5
Pig waste	6.1	3.4	6.2	5.7	14.7	7.2
Control	5.4	3.0	6.0	5.8	13.4	6.7
Mean	5.8	3.3	6.3	5.9	14.6	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 0.8

LSD (0.05) Variety = 0.8

LSD (0.05) Manure sources x variety = 1.6

The effect of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on number of calyx of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Table 11. Cattle dung amendment increased number of calyx in *S. aethiopicum* and *S. Ex-Lantan*, while poultry manure increased number of calyx in *S.gilo*, *S. macrocarpon* and *S. melongena*. The different manure sources showed no significant differences in mean number of calyx. The application of the different organic manure sources showed no significant effect on the number of calyx of garden egg. Although the different garden egg varieties were not significantly different in terms of number of calyx, *Solanum gilo* recorded the highest mean value of 5.4. Application of poultry manure also gave the mean highest number of calyx (5.3). Relative to control, there were slight increases in the number of calyx in plots treated with organic manure. This shows that organic manure application has the ability to improve the growth and yield attributes of garden egg. Poultry manure has profound effect on the vegetative development of garden egg and it ensures healthy and vigorous growth of the crop (Aliyu , 2010).

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Table 11: Effect of different organic amendment and garden egg varieties on mean number of calyx of garden egg in 2012 and 2013

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex - lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpo n</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	5.2	5.1	5.2	5.1	5.0	5.1
Poultry manure	5.6	5.0	5.0	5.7	5.2	5.3
Pig waste	5.5	5.0	5.0	5.3	5.1	5.2
Control	5.2	5.0	5.0	5.1	5.0	5.0
Mean	5.4	5.0	5.0	5.3	5.1	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 0.2

LSD (0.05) Variety = 0.1

LSD (0.05) Manure sources x variety = 0.9

The effect of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on number of fruits of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown in Table 12. Poultry manure application significantly increased the number of fruits in all the garden egg varieties. The interaction effect between the organic manure sources and garden egg varieties were significant. The application of organic manure increased the number of fruits relative to the control. The interaction effect of poultry manure and *solanum aethiopicum* gave the highest number of fruits of 1412. *Solanum gilo* interaction with poultry manure produced the fruit number of 404 while the least value of 66 was recorded with interaction of *solanum melongena* and the control. The better performance in number of fruits of garden egg may be due to the release of more nutrients from the manure and improvement in soil properties. (Dauda *et al.*, 2008) reported that poultry manure promotes vigorous growth, increase meristematic and physiological activities in the plant due to supply of plant nutrient and improvement in soil properties. These often result in the synthesis of more photo assimilates which are used in producing fruits.

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Table 12: Effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean number of fruits of garden egg in 2012 and 2013

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex - Lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpo n</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	360	1204	300	155	96	423
Poultry manure	404	1412	314	282	120	506
Pig waste	293	1361	252	210	76	436
Control	216	1024	189	164	66	334
Mean	318	1250	264	203	89	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 69.0

LSD (0.05) Variety = 97.8

LSD (0.05) Manure sources x variety = 186.4

The effect of organic amendments and garden egg varieties on fruit weight of garden egg in 2012 and 2013 is shown on Table 13. The garden egg varieties responded differently to the organic amendments. Cattle dung amendment increased fruit weight in *S. melongena* plot. Poultry manure increased fruit in *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. macrocarpon* plots while pig waste application increased fruit weight in *S.gilo* and *S. aethiopicum* plot. There were significant differences between cattle dung and poultry manure in *S. gilo* and *S. macrocarpon* plots. There were significant interaction between the different manure sources and garden egg varieties. The manure sources increased the fruit weight of the garden egg varieties relative to the control. The interaction effect of piggery waste and *Solanum gilo* recorded the highest fruit weight of 9.95 t/ha while the least value (2.12 t/ha) was records with the interaction of the control and *Solanum aethiopicum*. The applications of organic amendments were able to improve the soil properties and hence, the fruit weight of garden egg. (Dauda *et al.*, 2008), reported that poultry manure supplies nutrients that enhance vigorous growth that culminates in increase in fruit yield.

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Table 13: Effect of different organic amendments and garden egg varieties on mean/fruit weight (t/ha) of garden egg in 2012 and 2013

Organic Amendments	<i>Solanum gilo</i>	<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>	<i>Solanum Ex - lantan</i>	<i>Solanum macrocarpon</i>	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Mean
Cattle dung	6.3	2.2	8.3	2.8	9.1	5.7
Poultry manure	8.7	2.5	9.3	4.1	8.5	6.6
Pig waste	10.0	2.8	5.9	3.8	5.9	5.6
Control	4.6	2.1	5.4	3.8	7.4	4.7
Mean	7.4	2.3	7.2	3.6	7.8	

LSD (0.05) Manure = 1.6

LSD (0.05) Variety = 2.1

LSD (0.05) Manure sources x variety = 4.1

Conclusion

The results obtained from the study showed that the different organic amendments increased soil pH, and N, P, K, Ca, Mg values while soil texture virtually remained unchanged. Better yield and growth were recorded with poultry manure more than pig waste and cattle dung applications. In plots treated with poultry manure, number of leaves, number of branches and plant height at 4, 6 and 8 WAT was highest in plots with *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, *S. macrocarpon* and *S. Ex-Lantan*. Moreso, plots with *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, *S. Ex-Lantan* and *S. macrocarpon*, treated with poultry manure favoured number of fruits. Cattle dung application increased fruit girth in plots planted to *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon* while pig waste showed increased fruit weight and fruit length in plots with *S. gilo* and *S. aethiopicum*.

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